

Comparative Assessment of Scalpel vs. Diathermy use in midline incision for Laparotomy with respect to blood loss and incision time.

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Abstract:

Objective: The main aim of this study was to do the comparative assessment of scalpel vs. diathermy use in midline incision for laparotomy with respect to blood loss and incision time.

Place and Duration of Study: This study was carried out in a duration of 5 months from March 2019 to July 2019 Mayo hospital Lahore.

Materials and Methods: For our prospective randomized study, a total of 50 patients were selected. 2 groups were made and 25 people were in scalpel group and 25 in diathermy group. Both groups were evaluated for blood loss and incision time. All the patients with the ages between 18-70 years of either gender were included in this study. Patients either presenting in outdoor or emergency requiring laparotomy via midline were included.

Exclusion criteria: Those patients who had deranged coagulation profile, clotting or bleeding disorders or history of blood thinner use were excluded from this study.

Results: There were 2 groups and each group had 25 patients. Mean age of the patients in scalpel group was 44 years and mean age of patients in diathermy group was 43 years which is not a significant difference. Among these patients 60% were male and 40% were female. Male patients had a mean age of 43 years while it was 44 years in female patients which is also not significant.

No significant difference was seen in both groups regarding incision time (P value 0.009). However while calculating the blood loss it was seen that blood loss was more in scalpel group as compared to diathermy group (P value 0.000).

Conclusion: Among these two methods, superior one is diathermy for making an incision as compared to scalpel regarding blood loss but while considering time taken for making an incision none is above the other one.

Keywords: Skin incision, Blood loss, scalpel, diathermy

Introduction: Traditionally scalpel is used by general surgeons to make an incision. Use of scalpel results in excessive bleeding as well as increased operating time. About 100 years ago cautery was introduced. Initially it was used only for maintaining hemostasis. In early times, making incisions using cautery was debatable among surgeons due to increased wound healing time and fright of burning the skin. Multiple studies have been done to proclaim this presumption. But with the advances in cautery units over the time have increased the use in making incisions due to decreased blood loss and operating time. Big incisions like laparotomy incision take ample amount of time to allow full exposure.

Materials and Methods: For our prospective randomized study, a total of 50 patients were selected. 2 groups were made and 25 people were in scalpel group and 25 in diathermy group. Both groups were evaluated for blood loss and incision time. All the patients with the ages between 18-70 years of either gender were included in this study. Patients either presenting in outdoor or emergency requiring laparotomy via midline were included.

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Table 1. Age distribution of patients in each groups (n=50)

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	p-value
Age (in Diathermy years) group	25	43.08	11.339	0.516
Scalpel group	25	45.00	9.309	

Table 2. Age distribution according to gender of patients in our study (n=50)

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age (in Female years)	20	44.75	9.596
Male	30	43.57	10.900
p-value	0.695		

Table 3. Age distribution according to gender of patients in diathermy group (n=25)

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age (in Female years)	10	49.1	8.17
Male	15	44.8	12.5
p-value	0.743		

Table 4. Age distribution according to gender of patients in scalpel group (n=25)

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age Female	11	40.4	9.2
Male	14	42.2	9.20
p-value	0.818		

Table 5. Diathermy versus scalpel in midline laparotomy incision

Operative parameters	Diathermy (25)	Scalpel (25)	p value
Incision time (minutes)	18.20±6.94	15.48±4.02	0.096
Blood loss (gm)	10.36±4.37	23.04±7.04	0.000

No significant difference was seen in both groups regarding incision time (P value 0.009). However while calculating the blood loss it was seen that blood loss was more in scalpel group as compared to diathermy group (P value 0.000).

Discussion: As stated earlier, due to poor wound healing and fright of burn, surgeons are hesitant to use cautery for making an incision. Johnson and Serpell used cautery for making an incision of skin but they did not use it for incising deeper layers. This study is in contrast to our study as we used cautery to incise not only skin but deeper layers like subcutaneous, muscle tissues. There were two groups in our study having 25 candidates in each group. One group was scalpel group and other was diathermy group. Both these groups were identical

and there was no difference in terms of gender and age. According to our study less blood loss was seen in diathermy group as compared to scalpel group. Similar findings were seen in a study conducted by Kearns et al in which they showed that less blood seen is seen in diathermy group. Decreased blood loss in diathermy group is due to the sealing of blood vessels by coagulation while making the incision.

Keeping time in consideration, no significant difference was seen in our study among these two groups. Time taken for making an incision using cautery and scalpel had no difference. The findings of our study is in contrast with the one conducted by Dixon et al in which he showed that using cautery for making an incision takes less time as

compared to scalpel. The increased time was due to the factor that it takes much time for sealing the blood vessels which is not a case in incision with cautery. According to our study, in the hands of expert diathermy and scalpel use has no difference in time duration.

Conclusion: Among these two methods, superior one is diathermy for making an incision as compared to scalpel regarding blood loss but while considering time taken for making an incision none is above the other one.

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